

Assessment of Library Resources and Services: B-School Patron Expectations and Satisfactions- A Pilot Study

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Abstract

Purpose: The study aimed to assess user expectations and satisfaction with library resources, services, and infrastructure at Hyderabad B-Schools. It focused on how well services meet academic and research needs, satisfaction with digital and print resources, staff, infrastructure, and sustainability. It also identified gaps between user expectations and actual services.

Methodology: The study used a survey with multistage cluster sampling. Data was collected via questionnaires distributed in person and library usage stats. The survey targeted students, faculty, and staff at B-schools, focusing on PGDM and PGP students. A 30-question structured questionnaire covered library resources, services, infrastructure, and staff support. Respondents used a 5-point Likert scale to assess their expectations, satisfaction, and any issues. Data from 100 respondents was analysed with Excel and SPSS.

Findings: The study reveals that students frequently use the library, followed by staff and faculty, spending approximately an hour daily, indicating steady engagement. Students use the internet for academic and entertainment purposes, while faculty focus on research. Patrons are highly satisfied with Print and E-resources, but AV collections need improvement. The eco-friendly infrastructure and knowledgeable staff generally meet users' expectations. Overall, users are satisfied, with recommendations for digital tools, AV materials, and individual workspaces.

Conclusion: Academic libraries support the activities, programs, and research of institutions. User satisfaction, essential for measuring service quality, reflects the accessibility of resources, information, and patronage in academic environments. Assessing satisfaction helps improve services and identify areas for enhancement. The primary goal is to meet educational needs by providing excellent services and enhancing user satisfaction.

Study type: Research paper

Keywords: Library Resources, Library Services, User Expectations, B-School Library, User Satisfaction, Library Assessment

Introduction

The evolution of management education in India has steadily progressed over the past 70 years. Since the economic liberalisation of the 1990s and subsequent significant economic growth and globalisation, there has been a heightened demand for MBA programmes. This

led to the entry of many institutions offering MBA courses across the country. Currently, over 4, 4000 management institutions provide MBA education alongside globally recognised establishments such as IIMs and ISB. Business schools are continually striving to develop future leaders to meet the challenges of the business world. Over the past 25 years, Hyderabad has experienced substantial growth in new business schools, establishing itself as a centre of knowledge for educational institutions and hosting a world- renowned business school, the Indian School of Business. Additionally, the city is home to other notable B- Schools such as Vignana Jyothi Institute of Management (VJIM), Institute of Public Enterprise (IPE), Administrative Staff College of India (ASCI), Siva Sivani Institute of Management (SSIM), Institute of Management Technology (IMT), Narsee Monjee Institute of Management Studies (NMIMS), Woxsen Business School, Sagar Global Business School (SGBS), Dhruva College of Management, GITAM Hyderabad Business School (HBS), and ICFAI Business School (IBS), all dedicated to providing high- quality education to aspiring managers. Meanwhile, investment in technology companies like Infosys, TCS, Google, and various Fintech ventures has increased the demand for skilled management professionals. Hyderabad, often called Pearl City, has become a hub for the burgeoning IT sector.

The culturally significant city of Hyderabad has developed into a vibrant centre for education, driven largely by remarkable growth in the sector. Recognising the importance of educational demand, it is the library's responsibility to align with the institute's vision in nurturing future leaders by delivering an exceptional user experience. Academic libraries have faced increasing pressure to adopt new technologies, adapt to changing academic practices, and meet the evolving needs of their users. Business school libraries, in particular, must cater to their patrons' specific requirements, who often seek access to high-quality financial databases, case studies, industry reports, and business journals. A thorough understanding of patron expectations and satisfaction levels is vital for library managers to make well-informed decisions regarding resource allocation, service enhancements, and future planning. This study aims to identify the gaps between what B-school patrons expect from their library services and resources and their satisfaction with the current offerings. The results will help library staff recognise the strengths and weaknesses of existing services and guide future improvements.

Objectives of this Study

The study's overall goal was to assess library resources and Services in the B-schools of Hyderabad City based on Users' Expectations and Satisfaction. Specific objectives are to:

1. To examine students' habits in utilising library resources.
2. To understand users' expectations of the library.
3. To evaluate the extent of library resource usage among respondents.
4. To analyse respondents' engagement with library services.
5. To review the condition and adequacy of library infrastructure.
6. To assess the support, expertise, and responsiveness of library staff.

Methodology

The study employed a survey-based methodology using a multistage cluster sampling technique. Data was collected by personally distributing questionnaires and analysing library usage statistics. The survey targeted three main patron groups in B-Schools—students, faculty, and non-teaching staff—focusing primarily on PGDM and PGP students. A structured questionnaire with 30 questions was developed, covering areas such as library resources, services, infrastructure, and staff support. Respondents answered using a 5-point Likert scale to assess the alignment between their expectations and satisfaction, and to indicate any

problems or difficulties they faced. The data collected from 100 respondents was analysed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS.

Literature Review:

The literature review includes carefully selected publications that examine existing information in the field of the current investigation. Several studies have documented users' expectations when accessing library resources and services. The library is a preferred space for students to learn and engage in learning activities outside of class hours in any academic institution. Users often utilise libraries for individual or group studies, accessing computer facilities, retrieving necessary information, reading, socialising, attending meetings, and utilising reference and information services (Kim, 2017). A library serves as an academic hub where all students can receive the support needed for academic success (Lux et al., 2016). According to Dali, Vannier, and Douglass (2021), the term "Reading Experience Librarianship" aims to represent the diverse range of activities better and expanded roles of reader service librarians. It highlights the shift from in-house reader services and programmes for avid readers to genuine community engagement with broader goals, scope, and reach. Utilising academic library services and resources at least once during the academic year was linked to higher grade point averages (GPA) compared to peers who did not utilise these resources (Soria et al., 2014). "The libraries of Business Schools are dedicated not only to collecting but also to organising, preserving, and facilitating access to knowledge for everyone. Academic libraries, including those in Business Schools, play a vital role in advancing the missions of research and development in higher education."

These libraries support learning, teaching, research, and other educational activities that align with the goals of their respective institutions (Vijesh & Sreejith, 2020). Patrons see the library as a space for socialising, relaxation, and restoration, contrasting with its traditional role as a quiet place for reading and research (Waxman et al., 2007). According to Vijesh and Sreejith (2020), it is important to acknowledge the significant involvement that business school and management librarians can make in society. With their wealth of resources and services, academic librarians are well-equipped to contribute to meaningful outreach to the community. By doing so, they can ensure that the library remains a valuable resource for everyone, regardless of their background or identity (Kumar, Vandana, & Batra, 2018). Research has shown that students are generally aware of e-resources and find them beneficial for academic success. Notably, students tend to use free resources more often than paid ones due to a lack of exploration skills. Furthermore, a discipline-specific analysis has revealed that students in information technology, economics, and finance rely on e-resources more frequently than those studying marketing, operations, and human resource management. Similarly, faculty and training have been identified as influential factors in encouraging students to utilise e-resources. As academic libraries operate in a constantly changing environment, they must proactively implement new promotional and marketing strategies to reach their users and maintain the relevance of their services effectively (Babalhavaeji et al., 2010).

ISB and VJIM Libraries:

The library at ISB's Hyderabad campus, known as the Bajaj Auto Library, is specifically tailored to support the academic and research needs of the ISB community. As a knowledge hub, it offers a wide range of information resources, including the latest management books, print and online textbooks, and audio-visual materials. The library's efficient and responsive services are designed to meet the evolving needs of the academic community, which increasingly relies on electronic resources such as e-books, e-journals, and databases. The

VJIM Library provides a broad selection of modern knowledge resources and innovative information services, making it a valuable learning centre for both students and faculty. All library collections, including online databases, can be accessed through the institute's network. Users have the convenience of accessing online databases and checking the availability of library materials in real-time from their computer terminals. The library is committed to delivering top-quality information services to support the learning process, including OPAC, Circulation, Reference and Inter-Library Loans, Photocopying, and Database Search Services. Additionally, the library is an institutional member of DELNET.

Users in Academic Libraries:

The main fundamental purpose of a library is to serve users by providing all types of information needed by individual patrons. The library aims to meet the needs of its clientele across various services they wish to access. Users are regarded as primary recipients when assessing the quality of services offered by the academic library. Their feedback is crucial for understanding service quality and often helps justify the services provided. Users are categorised as faculty, researchers, students, external users, staff, and non-academic staff, with their requirements varying according to their profiles and interests. The primary focus for faculty and researchers in using the library is to support their research needs.

User Feedback:

User feedback is a systematic process of collecting user views about the library's services, resources, and infrastructure to enhance the user experience. It is crucial for assessing patron needs and providing improved services. (Porat, 2016) Implementing a systematic user feedback process has been proven advantageous for academic libraries, as it offers valuable insights into service, collection, and space-related issues. Academic libraries currently encounter various challenges from online information providers, document delivery services, multimedia products, and other competitive sources of information, all driven by ongoing innovations in information technology. "Academic libraries utilise surveys to gather patron feedback, which is widely regarded as a more reliable method for evaluating the effectiveness of library services. Consequently, library user surveys have become a common practice in academic libraries for assessing the quality of services offered to patrons (Adeniran, 2020). User feedback and analytics are vital for identifying the strengths and weaknesses of your library. They help improve user experience, service quality, functionality, and usage. Understanding patron satisfaction and expectations assists in identifying and resolving problems, as well as recognising new trends (Gyau, Liu, & Kwakye, 2021). Enhancing service quality greatly influences user satisfaction, whereas declining service quality results in reduced satisfaction. This emphasises the importance of academic libraries striving to deliver high-quality services to meet users' needs. It is essential for the library to maintain its current standards while continuously innovating to improve service quality and align with user expectations.

Results

The study analysed the data collected from the Patron of two B-Schools: ISB and VJIM. Data are presented in tabular form to determine expectations and Satisfaction.

Table 1: Level of Patrons Responded

Patron Levels	Total Responses	
	n	%
Faculty	29	29%
No-Teaching Staff	32	32%

Student	39	39%
Total	100	100%

Table 1 provides an overview of the percentage of questionnaire responses received from different patrons of the respective B-Schools involved in the pilot study. A total of 29 faculty members responded, accounting for 29% of the total responses. While this percentage is slightly lower than that of the non-teaching staff and students, it still reflects a meaningful contribution, indicating faculty engagement in the study. The 32 non-teaching staff members who participated represent 32% of the total responses. This higher percentage than that of the faculty may suggest greater interest or awareness among the non-teaching staff regarding library services. Students responded with 39 responses, which accounts for 39% of the total responses. This is a positive sign, as students are the primary users of library resources and services. The strong response rate from students is especially encouraging, as it suggests they are actively involved and invested in the study. Their feedback is vital for understanding how the library can better meet their needs, particularly in relation to digital resources, study spaces, and user experience.

Table 2: Usage of Library

Period	Total Responses	
	n	%
Below one-year	40	40%
Between 01- 02 years	30	30%
More than 02 years	30	30%
Total	100	100%

Table 2 offers insights into how long patrons from the B-School have been regularly using their library resources. Forty percent of respondents indicated that they have been using the library for 1 year, making this the largest segment of library users. A possible reason for this high percentage could be that these users are relatively new to the business school, such as newly joined students, faculty, and staff who have recently started engaging with the library's services. Thirty percent of respondents reported using the library for 1 to 2 years. This suggests that these patrons are likely studying or working with the library for between 1 and 2 years, indicating a moderate level of engagement. They may be utilising resources and services for more specialised or academic activities and could be quite familiar with the library's offerings. (Lux et al., 2016) states that the primary purpose of academic libraries is to support students and researchers in their academic pursuits. This aligns with the findings of Table 2, where library usage correlates with academic activity. Most users across all categories prefer to access the library to engage with academic content. The library, as a knowledge hub, offers space for group discussions and a quiet environment for study, along with printed and digital resources. The encouraging sign is that more than 60% of patrons have been using the library for over a year, indicating that the library is well integrated into their academic routines and supports their academic and research needs.

Table 3: Time Spent in the Library

Timing	Total Responses	
	n	%
30 minutes	34	34%
01 hour	52	52%
More than 02 hours	14	14%
Total	100	100%

Table 3 shows the daily time spent by B-School library users. This data highlights how much time visitors dedicate to the library each day and their engagement levels. The three time categories listed are 30 minutes, 1 hour, and more than 2 hours. A notable 34% of respondents said they spend exactly 30 minutes in the library daily. This group likely includes those who use the library for quick, focused activities such as reading course materials, borrowing books, or accessing online resources. Patrons in this category may visit for a short period to meet specific needs, but are not expected to stay longer. The majority, 52%, spend 1 hour per day in the library, showing that users dedicate a meaningful amount of time to academic tasks each day. Fourteen per cent of respondents spend more than 2 hours in the library, indicating that these patrons are involved in long-term research, exam preparation, project work, or teaching-related activities.

Table 4: Purpose for accessing the Internet in the Library

Patrons Details	Sports		Entertainment		Education		News		Health		Others		Total
	No	%	No.	%	No.	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	
Faculty	4	14%	0	0%	15	54%	6	21%	2	7%	1	4%	28
Non-Teaching Staff	3	9%	5	16%	7	22%	12	38%	3	9%	2	6%	32
Students	9	23%	13	33%	5	13%	4	10%	1	3%	8	20%	40

Table 4 provides an in-depth analysis of how different groups of patrons, including faculty, non-teaching staff, and students, use the institute's internet facilities on their own smart devices in the library. A significant 33% of students use the internet primarily for entertainment activities, such as browsing social media, engaging in leisure activities, streaming videos, and more. This shows that students visit the library not just for academic purposes but also for recreation and relaxation. Conversely, a majority of 54% of faculty members access the internet mainly for academic research activities, such as browsing literature, research data, online lectures, or other scholarly content to support their educational work. This highlights the crucial role of the library's internet in aiding the intellectual pursuits of faculty members. Additionally, approximately 38% of non-teaching staff reported using the internet to stay updated on current news and events, indicating that it is a valuable tool for keeping non-teaching staff informed.

Table 5: Library Resources and Services

Parameter	No Match		Slight Match		Medium Match		High Match		Very Match		High	
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %
The library has Sufficient printed materials for my work or study	0	0%	14	14%	27	27%	28	28%	31	31%		
All Electronic resources	0	0%	1	1%	43	43%	16	16%	40	40%		

available on-campus and off-campus remotely										
The library has AV resources for my work or study	0	0%	16	16%	41	41%	24	24%	19	19%
The library restricts access to websites that are not relevant to academics.	3	3%	12	12%	35	35%	32	32%	18	18%
The library regularly updates the contents on library websites	0	0%	1	1%	39	39%	26	26%	34	34%
The library has easy-to-use access tools/Discovery Services on my own	0	0%	11	11%	30	30%	32	32%	27	27%
The library has online tools/learning software to develop the patrons' knowledge.	0	0%	5	5%	49	49%	25	25%	21	21%
Library Online Catalogue (OPAC) allows me to renew/reserve the books, saving my time.	0	0%	10	10%	28	28%	25	25%	37	37%
Library has a proper bay guide to reach out the resources easily to library racks	0	0%	10	10%	36	36%	14	14%	40	40%

Table 5 presents a detailed assessment of library patrons' experiences with the library resources and services, focusing on their satisfaction levels and the extent to which these resources and services meet their expectations. The data is organized into various groups, revealing patrons' satisfaction with different aspects of the library. A significant 41% of users are highly satisfied with the availability of print materials in the library, indicating that the library

offers a large and suitable collection of printed materials to meet their academic needs. This suggests that the library is fulfilling the expectations of patrons who require print resources for their studies or academic work. Additionally, 40% of patrons express a preference for off-campus access to library resources, highlighting the importance of remote access, especially to e-resources, in today's academic environment. This underscores the value of remote access in an era where flexibility is crucial for patrons. Furthermore, 41% of users feel that the AV collections need improvement. Although the library provides AV resources, a substantial portion of users is not fully satisfied with the current collections and expects these resources to be upgraded to better serve their needs.

The restricted websites not relevant to the academic are attempted to access by 3% of users only, which suggests that most patrons follow the library restrictions and guidelines regarding internet use. It also specifies that the library adheres to the content filtering policies, which are largely efficient in confirming that the patrons mainly focus on the resources relevant to the academic. 39% of the patrons observed that the content on the library websites is updated regularly with relevant content, and 1% of the user's expectations are not met with the expectations. This signals that the library is doing a good performance of keeping its online portal up to date with the current content. Overall, 59% of users are highly and very highly satisfied with the library discovery services tools, which permit the users to easily access the materials and support to create a positive library experience. This high level of satisfaction specifies that the library's digital tools meet the requirements of most of its users and enhance the overall effective experience. The learning tools available on the library portal satisfied at the medium level of about 49% of users. This indicates that these tools may not fully meet the expectations of all users as its useful to limited users. The library's online public access catalogue (OPAC) service met the satisfaction of 62% of users, which expresses the ability to facilitate the renewal and reservations of library resources. This high level of satisfaction indicates that OPAC is a valuable tool for library transactions, which saves the time of the library patrons. 54% of patrons are happy with the Bay guide note, a tool that navigates the patrons to find the library resources and physical spaces easily. This shows that the library has efficiently applied a system that supports patrons in locating the materials quickly, and this large segment of user satisfaction indicates that the library provides a positive experience for its users.

Table 6: Library Infrastructure

Parameter	No Match		Slight Match		Medium Match		High Match		Very High Match		High
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	
The library has a silent space for individual activities	3	3.0%	9	9.0%	22	22.0%	26	26.0%	40	40.0%	
Library premises are designed to be environmentally sustainable	3	3.0%	9	9.0%	25	25.0%	28	28.0%	35	35.0%	
The library has adequate safety equipment	0	0.0%	8	8.0%	38	38%	24	24%	30	30%	

Table 6 presents a comprehensive assessment of users' expectations and satisfaction levels regarding the library's infrastructure facilities. This table reveals perceptions of the library's physical infrastructure and resources that align with users' needs. Twenty-two per cent of respondents feel that the library space moderately meets their expectations for individual activities. At the same time, a notable 40% indicate that the library provides a quiet space for their personal activities. However, overall, 11% of respondents feel that the library areas are inadequate and could benefit from further improvements. This suggests that most respondents are satisfied with the library spaces for personal work or quiet study; however, there remains room for improvement. Sixty-three per cent of respondents are highly satisfied with the environmentally sustainable aspects of the library, such as cleanliness, lighting, temperature control, and overall environment. A well-maintained library environment fosters a positive atmosphere for research and study, and this high level of satisfaction indicates that the institute's library has successfully created a convenient and welcoming space for patrons. The level of satisfaction with the library's safety equipment and precautions is 54%. This demonstrates that half of the respondents feel confident that the library is equipped with appropriate safety measures, including emergency exits, security systems, fire alarms, and other safety tools, ensuring a secure environment for users. Safety is a crucial component of any public space, and this high satisfaction level suggests that the library is effectively maintaining a safe environment. However, 38% of respondents report that their expectations are only moderately met, indicating a need for improvement in this area. Regarding sustainable infrastructure, a small but significant 9% of respondents still desire more eco-friendly practices. This suggests that a minority of users advocate for the greater integration of sustainable practices in library infrastructure, including green spaces, waste reduction initiatives, sustainable building materials, and energy-efficient lighting. This reflects a community-wide trend towards eco-awareness and sustainability.

The library can consider implementing additional sustainable initiatives to meet these user expectations. Additionally, a small segment of 9% of respondents requests explicitly more space for personal activities. While most respondents are satisfied with the current facilities, increasing dedicated spaces for individual work could attract more visitors to the library. Overall, Table 6 shows that the library's infrastructure largely meets or exceeds the expectations of most patrons in terms of environment, infrastructure, and safety. Nonetheless, a minority of users hold higher expectations for the library spaces, suggesting that investment in physical infrastructure may be necessary to better address these demands.

Table 7: Library Staff

Parameter	No Match		Slight Match		Medium Match		High Match		Very High Match	
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %
Library staff has sufficient subject skills to support the users'	0	0%	8	8.0%	22	22.0%	23	23.0%	47	47.0%
Library staff is always ready to respond to	0	0.0%	9	9.0%	23	23.0%	23	23.0%	45	45.0%

users'										
questions										
promptly										
Library staff	0	0.0%	17	17.0%	23	23.0%	17	17.0%	43	43.0%
encourages										
and										
motivates										
the patrons										
to visit the										
library.										

Table 7 provides an analysis of the skills of library staff and their ability to meet patrons' expectations. It examines various aspects of staff performance, including subject proficiency and responsiveness to patron queries, which motivates patrons to visit the library. 22% of respondents indicated that a medium match with the subject proficiency of the library staff suggests that, although most respondents believe the staff demonstrate satisfactory skills in some areas, there may be a perception among some patrons that improvements are needed to better align the staff's subject expertise with their specific needs. 23% of respondents feel that the staff's skills are highly aligned, and 47% believe there is a very high alignment, reflecting a positive response from patrons and indicating that a significant proportion find the staff possess strong subject knowledge relevant to their research and academic requirements. Overall, 92% of respondents are satisfied with the library staff's subject skills. This high percentage shows that most patrons are very pleased with the staff's subject expertise.

The promptness of library staff in responding to patron reference queries was reported by 23% of respondents as a moderate match. This suggests that although many users are satisfied with the promptness of staff responses, a segment of patrons feels that the library staff could improve in providing quicker replies. No respondents reported a no match, indicating that no patrons perceive the library staff as delayed or unresponsive. This is a positive sign that the staff are generally viewed as prompt and attentive. Overall, the lack of negative feedback combined with a moderate level of satisfaction shows that the staff are approachable and quick to assist, fostering a supportive and positive library environment. 17% of respondents feel a slight match with the library staff's ability to motivate patrons to visit the library. This indicates that some patrons do not feel strongly encouraged by the staff to visit, though this constitutes a small portion. It suggests that most patrons find the staff somewhat inspiring, but motivation might not be the main reason for their visit. Conversely, 43% of respondents report a very high match, indicating that library staff have a strong influence on a significant portion of patrons' experiences with using library resources and services. This demonstrates the positive impact library staff can have in motivating patrons to engage with the library and its offerings.

The observation emphasises the role of library staff not only in providing technical assistance but also in fostering an inspiring environment and creating a welcoming atmosphere that encourages patrons to engage more with library resources. Table 7 shows that the library staff plays a vital role in meeting patrons' expectations, particularly regarding subject expertise and the motivation they provide. Many patrons are very satisfied with the subject knowledge of the library staff, with 92% expressing approval. Additionally, the staff's approachability in handling user queries is very positive, and no respondents expressed dissatisfaction, although there is room for improvement in offering quicker responses for some patrons. Regarding encouraging users to visit the library, a significant portion of respondents feel strongly motivated by the staff, although a smaller group feels less encouraged. Overall, the skills and service levels of

the library staff are well aligned with user expectations, contributing to a positive library experience.

Discussion:

The findings of this pilot study provide valuable insights into the expectations and satisfaction levels of B-School library users in Hyderabad, particularly at ISB and VJIM. The high satisfaction expressed by users across all categories—students, faculty, and non-teaching staff—confirms the vital role that academic libraries play in supporting research, learning, and professional development in management education. This aligns with earlier studies (Lux et al., 2016; Soria et al., 2014), which emphasise that regular library use positively impacts academic achievement and student success. A key observation is the strong appreciation for both print and digital resources, especially the accessibility of e-resources both on and off campus. This flexibility is increasingly significant in today's academic environment, where students often participate in blended and remote learning. However, the relatively lower satisfaction with audio-visual (AV) resources indicates a gap that needs addressing. Since AV materials are essential for interactive and modern teaching, improving their availability and relevance could greatly enhance user experience.

The study also showed that students often use library internet access for entertainment, while faculty mostly utilise it for educational purposes. This dual use suggests that libraries need to balance their role as both academic environments and spaces that support student well-being. Creating designated zones for different activities—such as quiet study areas versus relaxed browsing zones—may better meet these diverse needs. Regarding infrastructure, most users were satisfied with the environmental sustainability and safety of library spaces. However, a small but notable portion expressed the desire for more individual study areas. This indicates a rising demand for personalised learning environments, aligning with trends in modern library design that emphasise flexibility, comfort, and user autonomy.

Staff support was rated highly, especially for subject knowledge and responsiveness, emphasising the value of human interaction in library services even in a digital age. However, some users felt less encouraged by staff to explore the library's full offerings, underlining the need for proactive outreach and engagement strategies such as personalised recommendations, workshops, and user orientation programmes.

Although this study shows a high overall satisfaction rate, it also highlights the importance of ongoing assessment and adaptation. The variety of patron needs requires more targeted services and the integration of emerging technologies. The findings also confirm the value of user feedback in guiding strategic improvements.

Being a pilot study, the scope was limited to two B-Schools and a relatively small sample size. Future research with broader geographic and institutional coverage could provide more generalisable insights. Nonetheless, this study establishes a strong foundation for understanding user expectations and enhancing library services in management education settings.

Conclusion

The study concludes that academic libraries in B-Schools, particularly ISB and VJIM in Hyderabad, play a vital role in supporting academic programmes and research activities. The majority of users, including students, faculty, and non-teaching staff, expressed high satisfaction with the library's print and digital resources. Access to electronic resources, especially off-campus, was valued, highlighting the importance of flexibility in the digital era. The library infrastructure, including silent study areas and environmentally sustainable design,

met most users' expectations. Staff members were praised for their subject expertise and prompt responsiveness to queries, positively impacting user experience. However, areas such as audio-visual resources, online learning tools, and individual workspaces received moderate satisfaction, indicating a need for enhancement. Some users also expressed a desire for more personal engagement and motivation from library staff. The findings show that, although overall service quality is high, ongoing efforts are necessary to sustain and improve user satisfaction. Regular usability assessments and feedback mechanisms can help identify emerging needs. Increasing awareness and providing training in the use of library resources can boost effective utilisation. Creating additional quiet zones or personal workspaces could attract more users. Incorporating further sustainability practices and technological upgrades would meet evolving user expectations. Ultimately, the study underlines the crucial role of academic libraries in enhancing the educational environment and advocates for strategic development to maintain excellence.

Suggestions For Further Improvement

The significant shifts in user preferences caused by the exposure to Information Communication Technology, Modernisation, and globalisation have greatly influenced users' expectations. Traditional services such as Current Awareness Services (CAS), Selective Dissemination of Information (SDI), Indexing, Bibliography listing, and other offerings are based on collection management. With the advent of information technology, these services have evolved rapidly, leading to the adoption of value-added services that align with the new library environment (Kinya & Daniel Muthee, 2022). Concepts of modern academic libraries are shifting towards creating information learning spaces that promote active collaboration among users. Dynamic technologies have modernised all sectors, including education and customer service in academic libraries. According to Yi et al. (2022), understanding how to utilise academic resources effectively can provide valuable insights for tailoring information services to meet the specific needs of individual users. As digital transformation continues to develop, academic librarians must prioritise understanding and supporting the unique requirements of their users by developing skills and knowledge of the latest trends and technologies.

The library could enhance perceptions of educational resources such as databases, e-journals, and academic articles available online through targeted promotion. Providing guides, seminars, or workshops on utilising library resources, especially for professional and academic advancement, could support increased usage for academic purposes. Emphasising the importance of research tools and encouraging the use of online databases through training sessions, workshops, and email notifications can be beneficial. Although patron satisfaction remains high, conducting regular usability tests can ensure that all users can access digital services effortlessly. Offering personalised service options for recurrent users could also enhance their overall experience. Consider creating additional individual study spaces by expanding existing areas within the library. Introducing more quiet study zones or soundproof booths for individual work, especially if space is limited, could be advantageous. Organising regular training sessions and workshops will help library staff improve their subject expertise and stay updated with the latest academic trends and resources.

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